

THE ADVANTAGE OF USING RIDDLES IN THE FORMATION OF LOGICAL COMPETENCES IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Kudyarova Artikgul

Student of the Faculty of primary education of
The Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz

Abstract. The article discusses the views of the pupils of the primary classes on the richness of speech, activity of speech, awareness, resourcefulness, agility, search ability and interest in proverbs and puzzles, which are the products of the oral creativity of the folk, and is subject to discussion.

Keywords: textbook, colloquial activity, teacher, reader, analysis, rhymes, riddles, labor, thought, agility, perseverance, ability to express one's own opinion, riddle, oral creativity of the people.

INTRODUCTION

The people expressed their conclusions, philosophical reasoning, which they received from their life experience through proverbs. Uzbek folk proverbs are diverse and diverse in theme. The proverb is an expression from the words of wisdom, which perfectly expresses the life experiences, conclusions of the people in artistic terms. The opinions and content that should be expressed in the articles will be widely covered. In our opinion, not a single event occurred in the existence of each proverb, which caused the event to be observed by a representative of our extremely intelligent, selective ancestors. The proverb is derived from the Arabic word “qavlun”, which means the concept of the word. Hence, the proverb can be taken in the

meaning of the word wisdom. When you ask each teenage boy about the Family, School, Motherland he will have little or no knowledge. It is also encountered in such cases that some elementary schoolchildren cannot independently, fully explain their thoughts, in their speeches three different excesses. Therefore, in order to overcome such problems, it will be of benefit to teach folk proverbs in order to clarify their speech. A lot of examples of proverbs, which are the product of folk oral creativity in the textbooks of primary classes, are elucidated.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

In the textbooks of primary classes, we can meet many proverbs on such topics as labor, seasons, motherland friendship, good and evil, respect for parents, adults. Here, we can take a look to some proverbs:

Yoz mevasi – qish xazinasi. (Summer fruit is a winter treasure.)

Toza havo – ming dardga davо. (Fresh air is a cure for a thousand troubles.) (1 class textbook “Native language and reading literacy”, p. 50).

With the help of the above proverbs, we give our readers an understanding of nature, encourage the younger generation to love nature, teach it not to hang, not to poison. Because from nature we emphasize our own breathing, that if we get dirty we get sick.

Kattaga hurmatda bo‘l, kichikka izzatda. (Be in respect of the adult, be in honor of the little one.)

Yaxshi so‘z qand yedirar, yomon so‘z pand yedirar. (2 class textbook “Native language and reading literacy”, p. 77)

RESULTS

The presented proverbs aimed to teach children to be kind, sweet, to respect the big and small as one, not to offend someone by saying hard, bad, on the contrary, to motivate him to rejoice.

Vatan ostonadan boshlanadi. (3 class textbook “Reading”, p. 15)

Halol mehnat yerda qolmas. (3 class textbook “Reading”, p. 15)

Kuch – birlikda. (3 class textbook “Reading”, p. 140)

It turns out that these folk Proverbs also serve to transport thoughts. Through these proverbs, we need to give readers a broader understanding of Motherland, diligence, mutual understanding, unity, we need to teach them to love the motherland, to protect it, to be a duck, to grow up as a faithful and worthy child in the future, and also to take into account the young characteristics of the pupils and to ask for examples of folk proverbs

Do‘stsiz boshim – tuzsiz oshim.

Mehnatli non shakar, mehnatsiz non zahar.

(4 class textbook “Reading”, p. 80)

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

These proverbs are about friendship and labor. When commenting on these proverbs, the teacher should explain to the readers what true friendship is. We need to teach to respect a friend, to be next to him, without leaving him when he worries about his head. A man who loves Labor should always be respected, everyone respects him, the bread found behind the Labor should be nondestructive and sweet, on the contrary, the bread found without honest labor should make a person suffer a thousand.

Through proverbs on various topics, which are presented in the textbooks of the primary classes, the worldview of students is established, their activity, linguistic competences are formed, perfection, moral perfection help them to become owners of such qualities.

One of the most amazing and smallest genres of folk oral creativity samples are riddles. This genre teaches children to be more observant, to know life perfectly, to be cynical. But it is not right to consider riddles in

folklore only in young children, since in riddles say and find competitions adults also participate with interest. The riddle is also a tradition to ask a few questions to determine what is hidden in the riddle contest. The side looking for the answer is from the narrator: "is there a soul or not?", "is it eaten?", "does it grow, does the master live?", something like asking questions tried to find the name. The question that can be solved in the riddles is expressed in a figurative form, and its meaning is hidden. In the riddles, the thing is traversed by analogy, mutual comparison, comparison with something else or phenomenon. The riddles are sometimes prose, often in poetic form, painfully and emotionally compact, simple and melodic.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, both proverbs and riddles, in addition to the upbringing of students, worldview, intellectual development, speech activity, good assimilation of the textbook, insightful, persuasive, examples of various subjects, provide a great help in educating representatives of the younger generation in the spirit of life-long, professional skills acquisition. Therefore, in the course of each lesson, it is clear to the reader that the passage of Proverbs and riddles along with the interpretation is a good effect. Then they will go into the depths of the proverb and the riddles, carefully looking for the content expressed in it. Folk proverbs and riddles have been serving to improve people's lives for many centuries. The more important they are in our distant past, the more important they are today, the more important they are even after independence. Folk proverbs and Riddles, which have a special place in the spiritual rise of the younger generation, become an important source for the development of oral and written speech of our little ones and live from centuries to centuries.

REFERENCES

1. I.Azimova, K.Mavlonova, S.Quronov, Sh.Tursun. Ona tili va o‘qish savodxonligi. 1-sinf uchundarslik 1-qism. Tashkent: Respublika ta’lim markazi, 2021. – 47-50-ps.
2. ЕРМАТОВА, Р. О. (2018). УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ВРЕМЕННЫМ УЧЕНИЕМ ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТОВ С ОБУЧЕНИЕМ ИНВАЛИДЫ. *Наука среди нас*, (7), 85-88.
3. Ermatova, R. O. (2018). ADVANTAGES OF THE TECHNIQUE" WHAT/HOW/WHY OUTLINES" IN DEVELOPING PRODUCTIVE SKILLS OF THE MEDICAL STUDENTS. *Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук*, (6), 69-71.
4. Utegenova, S., & Rozumova, D. (2024). DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING TAX AUDIT. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6).
5. Utegenova, S., & Mirzabaeva, U. (2024). TODAY'S IMPORTANCE AND PROSPECTS OF AUDIT ACTIVITIES IN UZBEKISTAN. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 4(6), 93-95.
6. Utegenova, S., & Oralbaeva, F. (2024). O‘zbekiston iqtisodiyotiga xorijiy investitsiyalar oqimini oshirishda mamlakatning investitsion muhiti jozibadorligini oshirish. *Журнал академических исследований нового Узбекистана*, 1(6), 131-134.
7. Khasanova, S., Akisheva, N., & Zholayeva, M. (2023). Methodological aspects of tax planning in the context of sustainable development. *Revista Gestão & Tecnologia*, 23(3), 286-298.
8. Маматқулов, Б. М., & Нематов, А. А. (2021). Ўзбекистон Республикаси аҳолиси орасида COVID-19 тарқалишининг хусусиятлари.

9. Abdullayeva, N. (2023). AHMAD YASSAWI SECT: THE ISSUE OF ZIKR AND THE STATUS OF ZAKIR. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 438-440.
10. Bazarov, S. (2024). JURNALIST VA BLOGERLAR NUTQI ETIKASI. *Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика*, 3(1), 36-39.
11. Norqulovich, S. H. (2023, October). NURILLO CHORINING BADIY ASARLARIDA MILLIY KOLORITGA XOS KO‘RINISHLAR NUTQIY JIHATDAN IFODALANISHI. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 25-29).
12. Ziyodullayeva, M., & Muxtorova, M. (2024). ABDULLA QODIRIY HAYOTI VA IJODIGA AYRIM CHIZGILAR. *NRJ*, 1(3), 860-863.
13. Muxtorova, M. (2024). MAXTUMQULI SHE’RIYATIDA AYTISHUV: AN’ANA VA IZDOSHLIK. *NRJ*, 1(3), 254-257.
14. Tajenova, G., Turdiyeva, G., Qurbanov, A., & Isakov, I. (2020). Current state and development of agricultural products exports of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Архив научных исследований*, (14).
15. Janabay, I., Gulbahar, T., Gulayda, T., Alisher, Q., & Ilkhambek, I. (2020). Current state and development of agricultural products exports of the republic of uzbekistan. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(8), 1684-1693.
16. Turdieva, G., Abishov, M., & Muratbaev, I. (2024). THE IMPACT OF CREDIT RISKS ON AN EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION IN THE FINANCIAL SERVICES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS. *NRJ*, 1(4), 215-225.
17. Beglenov, N., & Muratbaev, I. (2023). HOTEL SERVICES AS AN OBJECT OF STRATEGIC MARKETING ORIENTED TO THE

CONSUMER. *Science and Education in Karakalpakstan*, 32(2), 175-177.

- 18.** Xalmuratovich, B. S. (2024). JAHON AMALIYOTIDA AGROKLASTER TIZIMINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISH VA YURITISH BO ‘YICHA TO ‘PLANGAN TAJRIBALAR TAHLILI. *Scientific Journal of Actuarial Finance and Accounting*, 4(04), 140-150.
- 19.** Bayjanov, S. X., & Abishov, M. S. (2024). DEVELOPING THE ACTIVITY OF JOINT STOCK COMPANIES BY IMPROVING DIVIDEND POLICY. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 3(3), 94-97.
- 20.** Sultanov, B., Nurimbetov, T., Bayjanov, S., Seyilbekov, B., & Durmanov, A. (2023, October). Trends in change and the current state of the effectiveness of land reclamation measures in agriculture. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2921, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
- 21.** Байжанов, С. Х. (2023). ВНЕДРЕНИЕ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ В СЕЛЬСКОЕ ХОЗЯЙСТВО НОВОГО УЗБЕКИСТАНА. *BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMiy JURNALI*, 3(4), 51-53.
- 22.** Omonovna, E. R. (2023). KLINIK ATAMALAR SHAKLLANTIRISHDA SUFFIKSATSIYA USULI VA TA ‘LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARI. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 9(3), 198-204.
- 23.** Shodiyeva, G. (2024). O ‘ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILIDA SO ‘ZLARNI TURKUMLARGA AJRATISH MASALALARI. *Interpretation and researches*, (4 (26)).
- 24.** qizi Tursunova, M. A., & qizi Shodieva, G. N. (2023). MAIN INFLUENTIAL FACTORS TO LANGUAGE LEARNING

PROCESS. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(3 SPECIAL), 1181-1183.

25. Aliyeva, N., & qizi Shodiyeva, G. N. (2023). Ingliz Tilida So ‘Z Turkumlari Tasnifi Masalalari Sharhi. *Scholar*, 1(13), 22-27.

26. Navruza, A. (2023). INGLIZ TILI MORFOLOGIYASIDA SOZ TURKUMLARINI ORGANISH ZARURIYATI. *ITALY" ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION IN THE FACE OF MODERN CHALLENGES"*., 14(1).

27. I. Azimova, K. Mavlonova, S. Quronov, Sh. Tursun. Ona tili va o‘qish savodxonligi. 2-sinf uchundarslik 1-qism. Tashkent: Respublika ta’lim markazi, 2021. –77- 98-ps.